

IMAGODOLOGY AS AN INTERDISCIPLINARY FIELD OF RESEARCH: HISTORY, THEORY, METHODOLOGY

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Abstract. *The article examines imagology as an interdisciplinary field of humanities knowledge and analyzes its genesis, theoretical foundations, and methodological framework. Particular attention is paid to different interpretations of the concept of “imagology” in the modern academic environment, as well as to the analysis of the opposition between the image of “one’s own” and “the alien/Other” as a key concept in imagological research. The historical stages in the development of imagology are considered, beginning with its formation within comparative studies and ending with contemporary trends. Special attention is given to the contribution of Russian and foreign scholars to the formation and development of imagological studies.*

Keywords: *imagology, comparative studies, image, “one’s own,” “alien/Other,” ethnic stereotype, interdisciplinarity, literary studies, national character, cultural stereotypes, intercultural communication, identity.*

Introduction

In recent years, interest in imagology has increased in Russian humanities scholarship. Imagology is an interdisciplinary field that studies the image of the “Other,” a foreign country, people, and culture. This interest is caused by growing globalization, the intensification of intercultural contacts, and the need to understand the mechanisms through which ideas about other cultures are formed. Despite its growing popularity, the status of imagology remains debatable, and the concept itself is ambiguous, which requires a deeper analysis of its theoretical and methodological foundations. The purpose of this article is to analyze the history of the development of imagology, its theoretical and methodological foundations, to consider different approaches to defining this concept in contemporary academic literature, and to identify prospects for the further development of imagological research.

Methodology

The methodological basis of the study consists of comparative, historical-literary, cultural, and interdisciplinary approaches. The research is based on the analysis of scholarly works devoted to imagology, comparative studies, cultural stereotypes, and the opposition “one’s own 0 alien/Other.”

Results and Discussion

“Imagology as a branch of literary studies, from the Latin *imago* 0 picture, image” [Papilova, 2011, p. 31], makes it possible to study national and cultural stereotypes represented in literature and their influence on the formation of the image of the “alien/Other.” It is “a field of humanities knowledge that studies images of the ‘Other’” [Papilova, 2011, p. 31]. However, such

a definition requires clarification, since the concept of “image” itself is polysemantic and can be interpreted in different ways [Papilova, 2011, p. 32].

Some researchers regard imagology as “a branch of comparative studies concerned with the study of one people’s perceptions of another” [Oshchepkov, 2010, p. 251].

Within this approach, emphasis is placed on the comparative analysis of literary texts and other cultural artifacts in which images of foreign countries and peoples are formed and transmitted.

Imagology, as a scholarly discipline, emerged at the intersection of various disciplines, which determined the diversity of approaches to its definition. The most common definition of imagology is that it is a field of humanities knowledge that studies images of the “alien/Other.” However, such a definition requires clarification, since the concept of “image” itself is polysemantic and can be interpreted in different ways.

Some researchers consider imagology to be a branch of comparative studies concerned with the study of one people’s perceptions of another. Within this approach, emphasis is placed on the comparative analysis of literary texts and other cultural artifacts in which images of foreign countries and peoples are formed and transmitted. The main task of imagology in this case is to identify stereotypes, prejudices, and other distortions that arise in the process of intercultural communication. Other researchers, on the contrary, emphasize the interdisciplinary nature of imagology, pointing out that it relies on the achievements of such disciplines as history, ethnography, psychology, sociology, and cultural studies. Within this approach, imagology is viewed as a complex science that studies a wide range of phenomena associated with the formation and functioning of images of the “Other” in various spheres of social life.

“In the *Explanatory Dictionary of Social Science Terms*, imagology is defined as ‘the study of images’ and as ‘a component of the comparative-historical method in literary studies.’ However, this definition seems too general and does not reflect the full complexity and multifaceted nature of imagological research” [Yatsenko, 1999, p. 123].

“Contemporary researchers specify this definition by drawing attention to various aspects. For example, A. R. Oshchepkov understands imagology as a field of research that studies the image of the ‘alien/Other’ in social, cultural, and literary consciousness” [Oshchepkov, 2010, p. 33]. V. A. Khorev notes that “imagology studies the image of another people not only in literature, but also in other ‘texts’” [Khorev, 2012, p. 34]. N. P. Mikhalskaya believes that “imagology investigates the perception and embodiment in literary works of ideas about another country, its people, and the peculiarities of its national character” [Mikhalskaya, 1995, p. 45].

Several main approaches to defining the concept of “imagology” may be distinguished:

1. **The interdisciplinary approach:** imagology is a complex science that studies a wide range of phenomena connected with the formation and functioning of images of the “alien/Other” in various spheres of social life.
2. **The cultural-studies approach:** imagology is a field of research that studies the influence of culture on the formation of images of the “alien/Other.”
3. **The psychological approach:** imagology is a field of research that studies the psychological mechanisms involved in the formation of images of the “alien/Other.”

Imagology as an independent scholarly field took shape in the second half of the twentieth century. However, the prerequisites for its emergence had existed earlier. Interest in images of other countries and peoples can already be found in ancient literature and philosophy.

The formation of imagology is connected with the development of comparative studies in the twentieth century. It was within comparative literary studies that the foundations were laid for studying images of the “Other” in literary texts.

“An important role in the formation of imagology was played by the works of J. M. Carré and M. F. Guyard, who proposed analyzing not only the mutual influence of literatures, but also the way in which the image of the ‘Other’ is realized in the text” [Cerre, 1966; Giyard, 1981, p. 45]. They drew attention to the fact that literature is an important source of information about other countries and peoples; however, this information is often distorted and stereotypical.

“J. M. Carré and M. F. Guyard proposed a new method for studying literature, which consisted in analyzing not only the content of a text, but also its context. They believed that in order to understand the image of the Other, it is necessary to take into account the historical, social, and cultural factors that influenced its formation” [Cerre, 1966; Giyard, 1981, p. 45].

The Romanian researcher A. Dima urged scholars “to approach with the utmost care the portrait of a particular country in literature, since images of other countries cannot remain constant, and their creation is influenced by completely different factors, including whether the author of the text had experience of staying in the country he or she describes” [Dima, 1977, p. 45].

Gradually, imagology moved beyond the framework of comparative studies and began to develop as an interdisciplinary field of research. This was connected with the realization that images of the “alien/Other” are formed not only in literature, but also in other spheres of social life: history, politics, culture, art, the mass media, and so on.

The works of Russian scholars played an important role in the development of the interdisciplinary approach to imagology. M. M. Bakhtin developed the concept of the “dialogue of cultures,” which assumes that interaction with another culture contributes to a better understanding of one’s own culture [Bakhtin, 1979, p. 45]. “He emphasized that a foreign culture reveals itself fully and deeply only in the eyes of another culture” [Bakhtin, 1979, p. 45].

The Enlightenment had a significant influence on the development of imagology by popularizing the literary genre of travel writing. “Romanticism, as is well known, showed a profound interest in the national self-consciousness of a people, its language and folklore, the originality of its culture and literature, the mentality and character of a foreign nation, and the ‘exotic’ 0 ‘uncivilized’ peoples and savages” [Papilova, 2013, p. 67].

In the era of globalization, imagology acquires particular relevance. The intensification of intercultural contacts leads to increased interaction among different cultures. Under these conditions, understanding the mechanisms through which images of the “alien/Other” are formed becomes necessary for successful intercultural communication and for preventing conflicts on national and religious grounds.

Today, contemporary imagological research is characterized by an interdisciplinary approach, the use of new methods and technologies, and the expansion of its subject matter. In particular, considerable attention is paid to studying the influence of the mass media on the formation of images of the “alien/Other.” Images of various social groups and minorities are also studied. The processes involved in the formation of national identity and intercultural tolerance are analyzed.

It is necessary to identify the main tendencies and patterns that characterize the image of the Other; to explain why the image of the Other was formed in precisely this way; and to determine how this image influences intercultural communication and relations between different peoples and cultures.

“One of the key concepts of imagology is the opposition ‘one’s own 0 alien/Other’” [Stepanov, 1997; Khorev, 2012]. “It defines an opposition that permeates culture and shapes collective worldview. The image of the ‘alien/Other’ is always formed in comparison with the image of ‘one’s own’” [Stepanov, 1997; Khorev, 2012].

The distinction between “one’s own” and “the alien/Other” has existed since ancient times not only as a spatial and territorial boundary, but also as a difference in systems of beliefs and cultures. Attitudes toward the alien in each historically specific society were connected with the worldview characteristic of that society; therefore, the opposition between “one’s own” and “the alien/Other” had different content in each historical era.

In Stepanov’s work, the concept of “one’s own 0 alien/Other” is correlated with the concept of the archetype as a primary scheme of images, reproduced unconsciously and a priori shaping the activity of imagination, as “a multi-level structure 0 from the elementary images of individual works to entire literary movements and schools 0 permeating all world culture and at times endowed with internal antinomy” such as “paradise lost 0 paradise regained” [Stepanov, 1997, p. 67].

The study of the opposition “one’s own 0 alien/Other” makes it possible to reveal the mechanisms by which stereotypes and prejudices are formed, to understand how national identity is shaped, and to determine how the development of intercultural tolerance may be promoted.

Conclusion

Thus, imagology is an important interdisciplinary field of humanities research that studies the formation and functioning of images of the “Other.” Its development is connected with comparative literary studies, cultural studies, history, psychology, and sociology. The opposition “one’s own 0 alien/Other” remains one of the central concepts of imagology, as it helps reveal the mechanisms of stereotypes, national identity, and intercultural communication.

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